

The Position of Women in Manju Kapur's Select Novels

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Abstract

The present paper focuses on the position of women in Manju Kapur's select novels. Women have tried to bring in a new social order which is congenial to the physical, social and psychic well-being of women by demolishing the existing myths. They will be in a position to lead their lives with dignity and enjoy the full right of their free conscience to create their own values. The women of the 1940s had no voice to assert their rights. Manju Kapur raises the voice against male chauvinism to claim the rights of economic independence. She makes woman a cult figure which fights against taboos, social and joint family restrictions and constraints laid by patriarchy in the tradition. By analyzing the fictions of Manju Kapur, it is seen that the position of women in Indian social structure has been marginalized. However, Manju Kapur has created women protagonists who have tried their best to liberate themselves from the trap of patriarchal culture despite being subjugated.

Keywords: position, woman, right, Indian, social, family.

Manju Kapur deals with the position of woman as a daughter, a wife and a mother in all her novels. All her female protagonists hailing from middle class status challenge the existing social-cultural patriarchal system. In the social milieu, they are educated, modern intelligent, bold and assertive. Even though they try to transcend the social hierarchy by demolishing it, they often undergo serious psychological traumas in the absence of an alternative, planned feminist ideology that may give them freedom, security and peace of mind.

Manju Kapur provides a glimpse into the female psyche and deals with the full range of women experiences in all her novels such as *Married Woman*, *Difficult Daughter*, *Home*, *The Immigrant* and *Custody*. Demolishing the existing myths, women have tried to bring in a new social order which is congenial to the physical, social and psychic well-being of women. By that they will be in a position to lead their lives with dignity and enjoy the full right of their free conscience to create their own values. As one looks at the entire corpus of Indian women's writing in English we noticed that it is primarily a literature of the elite, for the elite and by the elite. Her characters are basically middle class and upper middle class women and novels are continuously looking for freedom from social and moral constraints. Tradition is deeply rooted in India and in the

traditional system Indian society is organized around gender division giving more space to male for dominance. Right from the marriage, the bride's incorporation into the family begins. She is guided and trained into the lifestyle of her husband's family. But despite of her all efforts to devote herself sincerely to the wellbeing of the family she is considered an outsider. Manju Kapur rightly says:

She didn't care so much about having a child now. These walls, this room was inimical to it. She wanted to be outside; she had had enough of inside. Slowly she left the apartment block, and started walking. The sky grey, a few brown leaves still clung to trees otherwise bare. (TI 172)

Although the quest for self, especially in the life of woman has become a much debatable phenomena, as long as this term is growing old, it is losing its authenticity. The literary geniuses who were born and nourished in the invisible shackles of traditions tried later on to break them and voiced their notions in a more liberated and out spoken manner in their literary works under the influence of modernism and Manju Kapur comes under this category of geniuses. The women characters in *The Immigrant* and *Custody*, have imaginative mind, longings and aspirations to soar high and high, the impressionism of new education and teaches and incessant urge to establish her identity. Kapur highlights the polluted environment, degrading human values and the Satanism of male against the weaker sex in her novel. Since time immemorial, Indian Women have unsuccessfully tried to create their own space in a patriarchal society. She registers her concern for Indian women in this novel. She dwells on various feministic issues in this novel like female education and their empowerment, financial independence, etc.

Manju Kapur's message is thunderous and clear that society would be better off if its females were effective and capable. According to the pioneer feminist, Simone de Beauvoir, "the two prerequisites for women's freedom are Economic independence and liberation from orthodox traditions of society. Kapur believes that the woman needs more than bread, butter and physical comfort." That shows in the ending words of *The Immigrant*, "She too was gearing towards fresh territories, a different set of circumstances, floating resident of the western world" (TI 334). As it is crystal clear to mention that prominent Indian women writers like Toru Dutt, Cornelia Sorabji, R.P. Jhabvala, Anita Desai, Shobha De, Kamala Das, and Manju Kapur have been primarily concerned with the issue of man woman relationship, which is nothing but a sad and realistic tale of a persecuted mind and physical and psychological torture in male-dominated society governed by rigid traditions and restrictions.

The sole objective of Manju Kapur has been the portrayal of the new image of woman, who fight against dejection, anger, oppression, exploitation, seduction, betrayal, rebel, longings, search for happiness, ironic social system and paradoxical tradition. Manju Kapur has presented the women of the 1940s, when women had no voice to assert their rights, most importantly the voice of the protagonist. She raises the voice against male chauvinism to claim the rights of economic independence. Manju Kapur makes the woman a cult figure that fights against taboos, social and joint family restrictions and constraints laid by patriarchy in the tradition. A major preoccupation in recent Indian Women's writings has been a delineation of inner life and subtle interpersonal relationship. In Indian culture and heritage, individualism, quest for identity, protests and concepts of rebelliousness have often remained alien ideas, as far as women were concerned.

Women were not supposed to raise voices for their rights, protest against injustice or question the already existing beliefs, customs, rituals and superstitions. They have to merely exist subjected to the patriarchal system. Women have to be obedient, quiet, submissive, and passive not claiming any of their rights neither as women nor as human beings. Even the earlier Indian women novelists have been portraying woman as the silent sufferers, the upholder of traditional values and ethics, a strict observer of social taboos, an essence of tolerance and patience, an exemplar to their

successors, a being with no space for herself, a woman without an identity, a worshipper of their counterparts, unfortunate and ignorant about their rights as human and so on. Manju Kapur is affected by her surroundings because we can see in some of her words. To look at women's lives from a feminist perspective is something, that is when imagination comes into it. Jane Austen is using a small microcosm to reflect every issue under the sun. Often, women's fiction is called domestic or family focused. It is a label that is not derogatory but a bit condescending. The theory of the feminism when applied to such novels for the proper critical evaluation may lead to different results. Portrayal of Shagun's character clearly shows the triumph of feminism. Beauvoir suggests: "the young girl has hardly more than her body which she can tell her own: it is the hardest treasure; the man enters her takes it from her; she is overpowered, forced to compliance, conquered" (405). A close study of Manju Kapur's novels create new vision on the world of female, in her all novels female protagonists projected as, an Indian woman in spite of her education, status an intelligence, tries to marry according to her choice, is likely to spoil her prospects in both the worlds, the one that she revolts against and the other she embraces. Any step taken by her choice condemned and rejected. These bring disastrous effect on lives on women. Her female protagonists are trapped between tradition and modernity in her middle class status. In her social setting they appear educated, modern, intelligent, sophisticated, courageous, and assertive. Their maladjustment in rapidly changing world makes them carve for more space for themselves. Hence they try to surpass the social norms. But mere efforts without clear objective, strong will power and planned action are not enough. She portrays the irritation, anguish and trails of Indian Middle class Women, who condemn social conventions and traditions. It clearly indicates the educated women have their own choice of career. Such women take divorce from her husband's and do not regret the outcome, because they find that there is so much in life apart from married life married life is not everything. One can do a lot service even a single woman or as a single parent.

Marriage is one of the tools for a creative writer to depict the cultural ethos representing Indianness. Manju Kapur has both opted for it and also cashed it. Marriage is a central theme in all her fictional works. Manju Kapur's every novel opens with a live discussion on marriage the topmost significant issue in the life of the female protagonist. Murali Manohar in his *Indian English Women's Fiction* keenly observes, "One of the main problems for educated women is marriage. Most of their problems are related to marriage" (Manohar, xiii).

The results of marriages in Manju Kapur's novels are not all the same. In *Difficult Daughters*, Kasturi turns out to be a passive sufferer being subjugated in a patriarchal family, Virmati is alienated, and Ida is single and childless. In *A Married Woman*, Astha in her restlessness turns into a lesbian and becomes reckless with everything including her children and her husband, and Peepalika a lesbian widow. In *Home* Nisha loses her economic freedom and independent identity. In *The Immigrant*, Nina being dishonest to her husband feels alienated in an alien land. In *Custody*, Shagun having everything from first marriage asks for divorce to run after her passion, and Ishita is divorced for her barrenness. The roots of the sufferings of these difficult lives in the fictional works of Manju Kapur are varied in nature. In *Difficult Daughters*, the problem with Kasturi is the socio-cultural background at her times, Virmati is in the dilemma, and Ida is too radical. In *A Married Woman*, Astha suffers because of her husband's negligence to her, and Peepalika's suffering can be traced back to her psychological weakness of being a single parent child.

In *Home*, Nisha suffers of the gender inequality in the patriarchal setup. In *The Immigrant* Nina suffers because of her husband's sexual impotence. In *Custody*, Shagun and Ishita both suffer for biological reasons one for passion and the other for barrenness. As a result, Manju Kapur has become the first and foremost Indian English writer to explore the theme of marriage to its fullest extent in the context of contemporary global Indian society and culture.

Manju Kapur in her fictional works has trapped the flux of a representative group of middle-class Indian women trapped in wed locks in different types of families. Her *Difficult Daughters* presents live discussions on wedding in an Arya Samaji agrarian joint family of Lala Diwan Chand. *A Married Woman* is about the marriage and married life of Astha, a Delhi based middle class Indian woman from a bureaucrat family. The *Home* describes the marriages in Delhi's mercantile family of Banwari Lal. *The Immigrant* is the projection of an NRI arranged marriage. Her most recent novel, *Custody* deals with the theme of failure of arranged marriage resulting into divorce and remarriage among the two divorcees.

Manju Kapur has clearly stated all possible reasons to marry through her protagonists. In *Difficult Daughters*, for Kasturi it is the responsibility, for Virmati it is to love and attachment, and for Ida it is to carry the line. In *A Married Woman*, Astha's parents want to marry her because they consider it as their duty. In *Home*, Nisha is married with Arvind only to serve his family. In *The Immigrant*, Nina's mother wants to marry her daughter so that she can get security and stability. And in *Custody*, for Shagun and Raman it is the standard line of beauty and brain, for Ishita and Suryakanta to be happy, for Shagun and Ashok to follow the passion, lastly to Raman and Ishita it is the adjustment.

Virmati in *Difficult Daughters* learns that in her family there is only marriage for girls. Even she perpetually recalls what her mother taught her to remember that "Still, it is the duty of every girl to get married" (DD 15). Manju Kapur's women are completely compelled to think of nothing but marriage as "It seemed to Virmati that her family could talk of nothing else but her wedding. Every word they said had so little relation to her inner life that she felt fraudulent even listening to them, passively, immorally silent" (DD 70). In case of Kasturi, the first generation woman in *Difficult Daughters*, marriage was to please one's in-laws. During Kasturi's formal schooling it was never forgotten that marriage was her destiny. After she graduated, her education continued at home. Her mother tried to ensure her future happiness by impeccable nature of her daughter's qualifications. She was going to please her in-laws. For Virmati's family, marriage is for the parental pleasure and family prestige:

Shakuntala Pehnji did not have five sisters waiting to get married either. And do you think it makes her mother happy to have her daughter unmarried? She may say what she likes about jobs and modern women, but I know how hard she still tries to find a husband for Shaku, and how bad she feels. You want to do the same to me? To your father and grandfather? (DD 58)

While commenting on her parental expectations, Virmati says that "They want nothing from me but an agreement to marry" (DD 100). When Virmati succeeds in getting married with her love the Professor, her feeling is not of joy and happiness but of being relieved of a guilty conscience. In the evening the wedding ceremony proceeded smoothly. The poet's parents did the kanya-daan, the seven pheras were taken, the couple pronounced man and wife. As Virmati rubbed her eyes, watering from the smoke, she knew, rather than felt, that the burden of the past five years had lifted (DD 202). Manju Verma in her article, "Manju Kapur's *Difficult Daughters*: A Study of her Women Characters" has aptly pointed out that,

The relationship between the two could have been an ideal between a man and a woman but unfortunately it becomes a story of an exploiter and an exploited, a union of un-equals, and an unusual tale of male chauvinism and woman's total submission. (Verma 76)

The study of the novel becomes clear that "Virmati had achieved through Harish, education, work, marriage and suffering" (DD 253). And the lesson is "Adjust, compromise, adapt." (DD 256)

There is another marriage in Custody between Ishita and Suryakanta, which fails because of Ishita's infertility. However the most interesting thing is Kapur's idea of bringing together two divorcees, Ishita and Raman as a flourishing couple. In this novel the reader could find Manju Kapur's own definition of marriage:

Marriage is when two people decide to live together forever. Should they change their minds they go to court and get marriage cancelled. Finished. Divorced. They become strangers; sometimes they never see each other again. (C 341)

The theme of marriage is central to all these novels. Though they deal with childhood, youth, old age, education, marriage is central. The focus is on the man-woman relationship i.e, Virmati and Professor Harish, Nisha and Arvind, Nina and Ananda and Astha and Hemant. Except the first which was a love marriage, all the others are arranged marriages. This reflects the major reality for Indian society. Manju Kapur gives voice to women's frustrations, disappointment, and alienation in a patriarchal world. It is a novel which provokes the readers' thoughts as to how Astha, a married woman in search of her identity, registers her protests against breathing patriarchal set up and emerges as an independent woman. Amar Nath Prasad observes in this context: "Women are no longer flowers of the pot for only decoration; rather they are fragrant flowers of the open garden diffusing aroma to all comers, braving the storms and rains" (qtd. in Gunjan 98).

As Astha realised, many facets in her relationship with her husband symbolized power than love whether it be sharing of ideas, sex, decision making, handling of finance, her own freedom and expression. It is true in all cases. Harish loved Virmati and pursued her but could never really grasp the pain she went through in being his lover. Ananda felt that an Indian wife would be understanding about his sexual dysfunction and never thought about how it would affect her physically and emotionally. It was not possible for him to accept his weakness and go for medical counselling with her. His behaviour with Nina, drove him away from her. Love was never a word between Arvind and Nisha and he had married her to please his mother. Of all the male characters the most difficult husband was Hemant. He was sex obsessed and used Astha for his pleasure. He considered her job to be useless, her poems to be neurotic, and her participation in public rallies as rabble rousing and called her and Pipeelika as mind fuckers. He travelled abroad four times a year and was angry and irritated when she was out of home. The money she acquired from the sale of her paintings, he insensitively used it to buy her flight tickets. In order to mount on the social ladder, he made her go from one party to another on New Year's Eve even though she was a little concerned. Ananda and Hemant also had extra marital relationships. Nina had found a blonde hair in her bedroom when she returned from India and Astha had found a condom in his suitcase after one of his trips. It affected the wives and shocked them about the hypocritical nature of their lives. Apart from love and arranged marriage, Manju Kapur also shows the extra marital affairs and premarital affairs. She shows the live-in relationship between Virmati and the Professor for a long time before marriage. There are really no issues she would not touch in her stories.

Manju Kapur openly discusses the reasons and consequences of deviant social behaviour. Finally it can be stated that Manju Kapur has explored the complex subject of the Indian family with much insight. Her women characters challenge the limits of passive and ordinary existence and try to choose more from life. They are characters who move to different destinations in search of their self.

By analyzing the fictions of Manju Kapur, it is seen that the position of women in Indian social structure has been marginalized. Manju Kapur has however created women protagonists who have tried their best to liberate themselves from the trap of patriarchal culture despite being subjugated and dominated by male chauvinism. She has exposed the existing irrationality in the patriarchal metaphysics in respect of women's status in society, through their exposition of the ills in the society. Women protagonists in these novels do not accept the definition given to them by

patriarchy. As their identity suffers from a male bias due to male dominance, they seek to demolish the existing myths of womanhood as prescribed by the male ideology. These new women are obsessed with total fulfilment rather than accepting the submissive domesticity.

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